

Heat Treatment of Anodic Oxide Films on Titanium and Niobium

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Heat treatment of the oxide films in air makes them more conducting. This effect depends on the time and temperature. Capacitance of titanium oxide films as well as niobium oxide films increases on annealing. The conductivity patterns before and after heating show similar trends and are of two types, the one associated with high conductance and lower rate of change of capacitance with increase in temperature and the other associated with low conductance and changes capacitance more rapidly with increase in temperature.

Heat treatment of anodic oxide films on valve metals has been the subject matter of research¹⁻⁴. Studies on heat treatment and quenching of anodised tantalum and the effect on its dielectric properties due to such a treatment^{1,2} are in accord with the known semiconducting properties of non-stoichiometric Ta₂O₅³. The effect of heating anodised titanium or niobium in air has not received much attention. Therefore, present investigations have been carried out with an aim to study the annealing effect of TiO₂ or Nb₂O₅ films and to examine the trends in conductivity profile during heat treatment.

Results and Discussion

The values of capacitance were measured after heating TiO₂ and Nb₂O₅ films for various intervals of time (2, 4, 6 and 8 h) at 308 and 548 K, and for this, films were formed upto different formation voltages (25, 50, 75 and 100 V) in mixed solution (1 : 1 by volume) of 100 mol m⁻³ Na₂HPO₄ + diethyleneglycol (DEG). At 308 K, there is no appreciable change of capacitance with time of heating, however, at 548 K, the capacitance of each of the film increases with duration of heating. Thus the heat treatment makes the films more conducting. After two hours, the change in capacitance is more for a 25 V film and decreases as the voltage of film formation (i.e. thickness) increases. Similar trends were shown by the films formed in other electrolyte solutions. The films formed in different electrolyte solutions are given in Table 1. The results show that the effect of heat treatment on oxide films is independent of the nature of electrolyte.

The effect of temperature of heating was studied by heating the titanium oxide films at different temperatures upto 573 K and niobium oxide films upto 623 K for a fixed interval of time (8 h). It was not possible to work beyond these temperature as the films got damaged. The plots of capacitance vs temperature of heating for the TiO₂ and Nb₂O₅ films formed in mixed solution of Na₂HPO₄ with DEG upto formation voltage 25 and 50 V are shown in Fig. 1. The capacitance of the oxide films does not change appreciably when heated upto about 423 K.

TABLE 1—CAPACITANCE OF 25 AND 50 V FILMS FORMED (TiO₂ AND Nb₂O₅ FILMS) IN VARIOUS ELECTROLYTES BEFORE AND AFTER HEATING FOR 8 h AT 548 K

Electrolyte	Film formation V	TiO ₂ film capacitance, × 10 ⁶ F		Nb ₂ O ₅ film capacitance, × 10 ⁶ F	
		Before heating	After heating	Before heating	After heating
		H ₃ PO ₄	25	2.66	2.96
	50	1.44	1.59	0.89	0.98
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	25	2.64	2.92	1.99	2.22
	50	1.10	1.24	0.91	0.99
Na ₂ HPO ₄	25	2.65	2.95	2.03	2.19
	50	1.07	1.21	0.90	1.01
H ₃ PO ₄ + DEG	25	3.82	4.20	2.61	3.01
	50	1.64	1.84	1.15	1.31
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O + DEG	25	3.64	3.99	2.48	2.82
	50	1.54	1.70	0.99	1.06
Na ₂ HPO ₄ + DEG	25	3.55	3.89	2.09	2.20
	50	1.58	1.75	0.99	1.07

Fig. 1. Variation of capacitance with temperature for (—) TiO₂ films and (---) Nb₂O₅ films, formed upto 25 and 50 V in 100 ml m⁻³ Na₂HPO₄ + DEG (1 : 1 by volume).

However, beyond this temperature, the capacitance increases almost linearly with rise in temperature of heating. Similar trends are shown by the films formed in other electrolyte solutions.

The conductivity profile across the TiO_2 or Nb_2O_5 film was studied by measuring the capacitance of heated as well as unheated oxide samples as a function of temperature in 38% H_2SO_4 in the temperature range 260–308 K. The TiO_2 film was heated upto 548 K while Nb_2O_5 film upto 590 K. The plots of capacitance vs temperature for films formed in H_3PO_4 , Na_2HPO_4 , $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 + \text{DEG}$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 + \text{DEG}$ (Fig. 2) show the conductivity profile to be of the two types, the one which is associated with low conductance and higher rate of change of capacitance with temperature and the other associated with high conductance and smaller rate of change of capacitance with temperature. The conduc-

Fig. 2. Variation of capacitance as a function of temperature for (A) heated and (B) unheated, (—) TiO_2 films and (---) Nb_2O_5 films formed in various electrolytes: (1) H_3PO_4 , (2) Na_2HPO_4 , (3) $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 + \text{DEG}$ and (4) $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 + \text{DEG}$.

tivity patterns for both unheated and heated samples show similar trends. Our results on conductivity profile do not agree with those of Smith and Tripp². This may probably be due to the non-availability of data for wide range of electrolytes at that time. The hypothetical break temperature (obtained by extrapolating the linear portions of the capacitance-temperature plot) is independent of nature of electrolyte/heat treatment.

When anodised titanium is heated in air, the metal extracts oxygen from the TiO_2 or Nb_2O_5 leaving the oxide oxygen-deficient. After sufficient heating, this deficiency reaches TiO_2 -air interface (or Nb_2O_5 -air interface) and an equilibrium is established such that an oxygen deficiency gradient is set up in the oxide. This gradient is maintained by the flow of oxygen from the atmosphere through the oxide and into the titanium (or niobium). The oxygen deficiency causes the oxygen vacancies with two trapped elec-

trons and these electrons could be thermally ionised thus causing the oxygen-deficient portion of TiO_2 (or Nb_2O_5) to exhibit n-type semiconductivity. Oxygen flow maintains the oxide composition both at the Ti-TiO_2 (or $\text{Nb-Nb}_2\text{O}_5$) and TiO_2 -air interface (or Nb_2O_5 -air interface) and is not affected by the nature of the electrolyte. The conductivity at any point in the film is dependent on the concentration of oxygen vacancies, $\text{O}^- 2e^-$, produced by the extraction of oxygen from the oxide by the titanium (or niobium) during heating. Therefore, increase in temperature increases the conductivity of film and this results in the decrease of effective thickness of the dielectric oxide. Hence, capacitance of film increases. The pattern of results of annealing of TiO_2 films is similar to that of annealing of Nb_2O_5 films. It emphasises that the same mechanism is operative in annealing of TiO_2 as well as Nb_2O_5 films.

Experimental

Titanium or niobium specimens ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$ in area) with a short tag were taken. The method of surface preparation and experimental set up for anodic polarisation was the same as described earlier⁵. The anodic oxidation was carried out in 100 mol m^{-3} H_3PO_4 , Na_2HPO_4 as well as in mixed solution (1 : 1 by volume) of 100 mol m^{-3} H_3PO_4 with diethyleneglycol (at a current density of 97.5 A m^{-2}) upto 25, 50, 75 and 100 V at 308 K. The capacitance was measured with a capacitance bridge at a frequency 1 kHz in respective electrolyte solution taking special care that the tags did not dip into the electrolytes. The anodised specimens after washing were separately heated in a pre-calibrated silica tube furnace in presence of air and at a constant temperature for different intervals of time. The specimens were allowed to cool and taken out and their capacitances measured in the respective solutions at 308 K. For studying conductivity profile, the cell was kept in a ultracryostat (model MK 70, G.D.R.) and the capacitances of the heated as well as unheated anodised specimens were measured as a function of temperature in 38% H_2SO_4 . Such an arrangement allowed temperature variation from 260 to 308 K.

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